

Haptic serial dependence in roughness perception and pleasantness

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Abstract— Our perception does not consist of isolated events but unfold and adapt over time, forming a continuous stream of experience. How we perceive an object is influenced not only by its intrinsic characteristics but also by our recent interactions, leading to sequential effects (i.e., serial dependence). In this study, we investigated whether such effects occur in haptic material perception, specifically in pleasantness and roughness. We also examined whether serial dependence is grounded in the physical object properties or the task at hand (i.e., perceptual attribute). To this end, we used seven sandpaper samples ranging in roughness (18.3 to 425 microns). In two separate sessions, individuals explored the samples with their index finger and rated how pleasant or rough each object feels. Our results revealed a significant attractive serial dependence in roughness judgments and a weaker repulsive serial dependence in pleasantness judgments. This shows distinct patterns of serial dependence for roughness and pleasantness emerging for the same physical stimuli. These divergent patterns for the same stimuli suggest that serial dependence in haptics is attribute-dependent, reflecting higher order mechanism rather than being purely driven by stimulus characteristics. Recognizing the role of serial dependence in haptics opens new avenues for haptic interfaces and engineering user experiences.

Index Terms—serial dependence, haptic perception, roughness, pleasantness

I. INTRODUCTION

Haptic perception is an integral part of human life helping with critical decisions, e.g., determining whether a surface is smooth or cool enough to touch. Unlike typical experiments, our perceptions are not isolated in trials but unfold and adapt in time to form a continuous stream of experience. How we perceive a stimulus in the present is determined not only by the characteristics of the stimulus itself, but also shaped by our recent interactions [1]. This is reflected in *serial dependence* – the tendency for perception to be influenced and shaped by perceptual history of recent

experiences. Serial dependence has attracted significant attention in visual perception research yet; it remains underexplored in haptics. In the present work, we investigated serial dependence in haptic materials.

In daily life, our perceptual system copes with noisy and ever-changing sensory input due to factors like shifting object properties, occlusions, and internal factors. Despite this, people usually perceive the world stable and coherent. This perceptual stability raises a fundamental question in perceptual science: how does the brain maintain consistency amid change? When variations are small, stability may be preserved because changes fall below perceptual thresholds [2], [3], are suppressed by the sensory system [4], or are filtered out due to limitations in attention or memory resources [5].

In the visual domain, serial dependence has been proposed as an active mechanism supporting this stability (see [6] for a perspective and [7] for a review). It typically manifests as an *attractive* bias – where the current stimuli are perceived as more similar to previous stimuli [1], [8]. For instance, an oriented gabor patch may be perceived to be tilted more leftward than normally would when the previous patch had a stronger left tilt [1]. In other words, *attractive* bias means that current stimuli are judged to be more like previous stimuli than to the ground truth due to systematic bias towards recent past experiences. As objects typically do not abruptly change their location and identity [9], [10], [11], serial dependence could enhance perceptual stability by taking an advantage of the autocorrelated and continuous nature of the world. Therefore, the perceptual system may exploit this temporal continuity by biasing current object representations toward recent ones resulting in a cost-efficient processing.

Serial dependence has been observed across a wide range of visual features and tasks. For example, it has been documented in numerosity [12], [13], motion direction [14], and color [15]. Nevertheless, serial dependence is not limited to simple features but also supports the perception of complex features. Notable examples include facial identity [16], facial beauty [17], attractiveness [18], aesthetic ratings of artwork [19]. Moreover, serial dependence extends to emotion – such as observer’s judgements of facial expression’s emotional intensity are biased toward expressions seen in the recent past [20]. Not only emotional intensity but also valence and arousal ratings have been found to be biased toward previous stimuli [21]. This suggests that serial dependence influences how we interpret emotional and social information along with how we perceive physical features.

However, serial dependence does not always operate as an attractive bias, a *repulsive* bias can occur, where current stimuli are perceived as more different from preceding ones (e.g., [22], [23], [24]). A notable example in tactile domain is the study by Hachen et al. [25], which demonstrated that

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judging the intensity of vibrotactile stimuli exhibited a repulsive history effect. Namely, current vibrations were more likely to be judged as strong following a weak prior stimulus, and vice versa. This effect of perceptual history extended beyond the previous trial and the earlier trials had quantifiable influence on the current trial albeit being weaker ([1], [20], [26], [27], see [28] for a review). This work, along with others, nicely demonstrates that serial dependence is not exclusive to vision but exists in tactile, auditory [29], olfactory [30] and affective domains [21], [22]. However, thus far, none of the studies investigated serial dependence in perception with active touch – haptics (see [25] for a tactile study). Haptics (i.e., active touch) is the cornerstone of our daily lives as it allows collecting dynamic information, bridging our actions and goals to perception. It plays an important part in building our continuous perceptual experience. Previous work has shown that manual explorations are shaped by previous experiences, which is known as *previous trial effect* [31]. This adaptive capability together with the daily relevance of haptics suggests that haptic perception during manual exploration could be subjected to serial dependence. Haptic perception can benefit from employing serial dependence in two distinct ways. First, attractive influences can help establish a continuous experience by smoothening the perceptual experience through bringing distinct percepts closer to each other. Second, it can perceptually increase the contrast between two percepts with repulsive influences, which might prove to be important when examining different materials or surfaces.

The primary goal of this study is to test whether serial dependence (SD) exists in haptic perception, particularly in pleasantness and roughness. Roughness represents a low-level perceptual attribute closely tied to physical stimulus properties, whereas pleasantness reflects a higher-level, affective evaluation of the same stimuli. Examining both allows us to test whether serial dependence in haptics is driven primarily by stimulus properties or by perceptual goals. In other words, we seek to investigate if serial dependence changes and adopts based on our goals for exploration or fixed for the explored object. To this end, we selected seven sandpapers in varying grit sizes, as they provide a controlled range of roughness. Participants completed two blocks where they judged the roughness or pleasantness of the same stimuli on two separate days. During the experiment, they explored each stimulus with their right index finger and rated its pleasantness or roughness, depending on the block.

II. METHODS

A. Participants

30 naïve individuals participated in the experiment (10 males and 20 females, $M_{age} = 24.867 \pm 4.09$, age range = 20-36). None reported any cutaneous impairments or sensory deficits. All participants demonstrated a two-point discrimination threshold of 3mm or better on the index finger of the right hand (i.e., dominant). Prior to the experiment, they provided a written informed consent, following the guidelines of the Declaration of Helsinki except preregistration. They were compensated with 8€/hour or course credit for their time.

B. Stimuli and apparatus

The stimuli consisted of seven sandpapers in grit sizes of 40, 60, 120, 240, 320, 600, and 1000 (425, 269, 125, 58.5, 46.2, 25.8, and 18.3 microns respectively) were used. All stimuli were mounted on a 10 cm × 10 cm wooden block, covering the entire surface of the block. The stimuli were presented on a plate holding a stimulus to avoid any movement and to keep the distance between participant and the stimuli constant. Participants sat at a table on which the plate was placed. An experimenter sat opposite to the participant to exchange the stimulus. Since sandpapers eventually wear off due to repeated exposure, they were replaced for every six participants.

Fig. 1. Illustration of the experimental setup. Left: a participant wearing headphones performing a trial. Right: Close-up illustration of the stimulus depicting a circular motion performed on the stimuli. Illustration is not on scale or depicts an actual stimulus used in the experiment.

The pleasantness and roughness of the stimuli was measured with a scale ranging from 0 to 100 (pleasantness: 0 – *very unpleasant*, 100 – *very pleasant*; roughness: 0 – *not at all*, 100 – *very*). Participants could respond with any positive number within this range including decimals. Potential auditory cues were blocked by headphones and visual cues were blocked by an occluder. The experiment was programmed in MATLAB 2022a (MathWorks Inc., 2007) using Psychtoolbox routines. A monitor was used to present instructions and a numpad to collect responses.

C. Design and procedure

The experiment employed a within-participants design with two conditions: roughness and pleasantness. Prior to the main task, participants completed the two-point touch discrimination task, which served as a screening measure to ensure sufficient tactile spatial acuity. The task was administered using a two-point discriminator consisting of two plastic disks with rounded-tip configurations. These configurations included either a single or two-tips (spaced 2-8 mm apart). For the purposes of this study, only the single tip and two-tip configurations with inter-tip distances of 2 to 4 mm were used, as a discrimination threshold of 4 mm or better was required. Each pattern was applied three times in a

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random order and participants indicated whether they perceived one or two tips. All participants were able to reliably discriminate between one and two tips at a distance of 3 mm.

In both conditions, upon completing the two-point touch discrimination, participants received the instructions, set at a table, and wore headphones (Fig. 1). During the experiment, in each trial, participants explored the randomly presented sandpaper samples with their dominant index finger in circular motion for 3 seconds, which was delineated by two beep sounds. Participants were instructed to apply light and consistent force, avoiding excessive pressure during the exploration. Upon exploration, they rated how pleasant (*very pleasant* to *very unpleasant*) or rough (*not at all* to *very*) the material felt. Each condition consisted of 168 randomized trials (7 sandpapers \times 24 repetitions), completed in a single session. The order of the two experimental conditions was randomized and took place on different days. We employed full randomization of trials as a conservative approach, rather than structured sequencing, which has not been shown to substantially increase serial dependence [1]. The total duration of each block was approximately 45 minutes including instructions and breaks.

D. Data analysis

We first took the logarithm of the physical roughness, which resulted in a mostly log-linear relationship with the perceptual ratings, excluding the last 5 trials of a participant due to a recording error.

Conventionally, serial dependence is estimated from response errors as a function of the stimulus difference between a trial and the preceding one. However, calculating such errors is not possible in the current study due to lack of ground truth for pleasantness ratings. For this reason, we quantified perceptual bias - defined as the relative perceptual change of roughness or pleasantness of a sample. We computed this by dividing ratings for each trial's rating by the participant-specific median rating of that stimulus. Thus, each stimulus has its own median per participant. This procedure expresses each trial as a deviation from that participant's median response to that stimulus. Plotting median of these biases against the physical roughness difference (per participant) between consecutive trials provides an analogous measure of serial dependence, indicating how relative sample ratings change as a function of the preceding trial. For example, the left panel of Fig. 2 shows the perceived roughness of different sandpapers while the right panel shows median biases as a function of change in physical roughness from the preceding trial. To quantify the influence of the previous trial on the perception of the next, we fitted a linear function (Fig. 2, right panel). The slope of the fitted function indicates the direction (attractive vs. repulsive) and strength of

serial dependence. For instance, if there is no serial dependence the linear fit would have a slope of zero. In

Fig. 2. Example data from a single participant: (left) perceived roughness as a function of grit size, and (right) the same data converted to show roughness bias as a function of roughness difference from the previous trial.

contrast, when there is a repulsive serial dependence, the slope would be negative and positive for an attractive serial dependence.

To make statistical inferences on serial dependence in roughness and pleasantness judgments, we conducted bootstrapping analyses [32] where we generated pseudo data by shuffling the order of trials for each participant 10000 times separately for roughness and pleasantness conditions.

This effectively removes any systematic relationship between the participants responses and the preceding trials. Then, we follow the same steps as the data to calculate the serial dependence strength. Next, we approximated a null distribution from the medians of 10000 pseudo groups by assigning each pseudo data generated from the same participant to a different group [1]. We deemed the observed serial dependence effects significant when they were stronger than the 95% of the approximated null distribution. This is equivalent to conducting a two-tailed one-sample Wilcoxon test against the estimated slope of 0. We followed the same approach for assessing the influence of older trials. We additionally used Holm-Bonferroni correction as we tested $n-1$ to $n-10$ which requires using partially overlapping data.

III. RESULTS

A. Serial dependence in haptic roughness and pleasantness

To test if serial dependence exists in haptic roughness and pleasantness judgments, we calculated the bias in roughness and pleasantness ratings as a function of roughness difference between stimuli in the currently rated and the previous trials. We estimated the strength of serial dependence from the slope of the best-fitting linear function (Fig. 2). A slope of 1 would indicate a perfect attractive serial dependence, as the rating would increase when the stimulus in the previous trial was rougher. Conversely, a slope of 0 would indicate that participants rated stimuli without any influence from the previous trial.

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To make statistical inferences on serial dependence in roughness and pleasantness judgments, we conducted bootstrapping analyses (see Data Analysis). We found a significant influence of the previous trial on both subsequent pleasantness ($p < 0.05$) and roughness ($p < 0.05$) judgments

Fig. 3. Strength of serial dependence for roughness and pleasantness judgments. Error bars show interquartile intervals with median.

(Fig. 3). In particular, the roughness judgments were significantly attracted towards previous trials while pleasantness judgments were repulsed from them (Fig. 3). Next, to test whether serial dependence is unique to the perceptual attribute or object, we directly compared the serial dependences for pleasantness and roughness judgments using a Wilcoxon signed-rank test. We found that the slopes for pleasantness and roughness were significantly different ($W(29) = 436$, $p < 0.001$, $d = 0.875$), suggesting different serial dependences for different attributes of the same objects.

B. How far back does perceptual history shape haptic perception?

After establishing the influence of the very recent perceptual history, we checked how far back the serial dependence reaches and shapes the present.

Fig. 4. Influence of preceding trials on subsequent roughness and pleasantness judgments. Shaded areas show interquartile intervals around the median. Solid lines show preceding trials with significant influence on the subsequent judgments.

To this end, we follow the same approach as before but analyze the pleasantness and roughness biases as a function of up to 4 trials back (Fig. 4). As expected, the serial dependence got weaker further along the perceptual history ([1], [27], see [28] for a review). Bootstrapping analyses with Holm-Bonferroni corrections indicated that both roughness and pleasantness judgments were significantly affected by the two trials back (n-2) trials back ($ps < 0.05$). Additionally, roughness judgments were influenced by the three back trials (n-3) ($p < 0.05$). Thus, both perceived pleasantness and roughness of the same haptic object are shaped by the recent perceptual history but in the opposite directions.

IV. DISCUSSION

In tactile domain, SD has been observed in vibrotaction [25]. However, to the best of our knowledge, the current work is among the first to investigate SD in humans within the haptic domain. In current work, we found that the previous trials biased subsequent judgments: roughness judgments were attracted towards the preceding stimuli, whereas pleasantness judgments were weakly repulsed from it. In other words, the perception of roughness became more similar to the previous stimulus, whereas the perception of pleasantness was contrasted from the previous stimulus. Further down the perceptual history, we found that serial dependence gradually decays. We note that while these effects are conceptually related to classical context effects (e.g., [33]) like assimilation and contrast, it should not be confused with them. Serial dependence specifically refers to short-term, trial-to-trial biases that emerge under randomized stimulus presentation rather than adaptation-based contextual effects (see [1] for detailed discussions).

Previous studies on emotional sounds, face expressions, and other images reported attractive serial dependence for pleasantness judgments in auditory and visual domains [21], [22], [34]. Here, we found a slight repulsive bias for judging the pleasantness of rough surfaces. One potential explanation for this divergence could be the difference in how stimuli elicit affective response: facial expressions, emotional pictures, and sounds provide rich and complex information to convey emotions through social cues, previous experiences, and semantics. In contrast, sandpapers are much simpler and do not necessarily have such connotations. Instead, they might invoke emotions through evolutionary mechanisms like survival [35]. Regardless, our results show serial dependence in affective responses to haptic objects and support an amodal account of serial dependence for emotions.

In contrast to pleasantness judgments, we found strong attractive bias in roughness judgments. Although there are no other directly comparable results, we argue that our results are in line with the wider serial dependence literature. Previous studies have shown serial dependence in various perceptual

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features, such as orientation [1], [2], [14] and numerosity [12], [13], which imply perceptual intensity. Similarly, haptic roughness can also be considered an intensity feature, as it can increase or decrease, as demonstrated in our study and many others (e.g., [36], [37]). Against the unifying intensity explanation, the amplitude judgments of vibrations seems to be repulsed when only the correct responses were considered [25]. However, because [25] excluded some of the previous trials, we argue that their results refer to a different history effect than serial dependence and not contradicting with the intensity explanation. Thus, our results corroborate evidence for attractive serial dependence for intensity features across visual and haptic modalities. Future research could extend these results by investigating how the strength of serial dependence scales with perceptual thresholds by adopting psychometric approaches like in serial dependence in visual perception [38].

Particularly, our results also suggest that the serial dependence is unique to the task at hand and not grounded in the object. In line with this, a previous study on face perception found an attractive effect on gender but repulsive effect on expression judgments for the same stimuli set [23]. Similarly, another study on visual orientation found serial dependence even when the task involved judging oriented dot clouds and gabors in interleaved trials [39]. Overall, task or attribute specificity of haptic serial dependence suggests that serial dependence might not be a purely sensory phenomenon bound to physical stimulus properties, but rather a flexible mechanism that shapes perception according to task demands. Additionally, we observed that temporally distant trials tended to have weaker influence on the current percept compared to more recent trials (see [28] for a review).

In two experiments we showed a perceptual effect in which previous haptic experiences shape later roughness and pleasantness judgments. While our focus was on the perceptual aspects, haptic exploration history can also shape perception in different ways. For instance, the haptic explorations such as how much force is applied or how the digits employed could change depending on the properties of the stimulus in the previous trial [31], [41]. We, however, argue that this manual adaptation is a consequence of change in purpose of exploration (task) or perceptual feedback. Our participants performed a single task (roughness or pleasantness) on different days. Therefore, we attribute any manual adaptations to perceptual feedback, which constitutes serial dependence. Future studies could measure exploration parameters (e.g., contact force and speed) to further characterize their effects. Nevertheless, our results indicate that the physical characteristics of stimuli is sufficiently informative to reveal haptic history effects.

We believe that this is especially useful for haptic

applications and designs. Here, we explore potential application opportunities that could leverage this perceptual mechanism and our findings. First, understanding how serial dependence works for different tasks and features can help designers to engineer haptic experiences that are both dynamic and continuous. Together with engineering techniques to enhance the continuity of displays (e.g., [43]), exploiting psychological phenomena like serial dependence could support the development of high resolution tactile displays at a little or no extra cost. For instance, interacting with rendered rough surfaces can be challenging to the user because of the abrasiveness (physical rendering) or numbing (vibration based tribological rendering) with constant stimulation. Similar results might be achieved by slowly changing the stimulation to build up the intended roughness perception using serial dependence. This can also help to reduce operational and other rendering costs since the roughness experience can be maintained while gradually reducing the intensity of the stimulation. Based on our results roughness perception is pulled towards the previous instance by 8% on average. Therefore, after rendering the intended roughness, the remaining updating cycles can slowly decay within the margins of serial dependence to maintain the intended experience. Another potential application is haptic/tactile guidance from visual aids to haptic touch screens. This is because serial dependence naturally pulls or pushes the perception to the mean of all percepts within a finite time window. Thus, serial dependence can improve haptic guidance and localization systems like how it shapes perception. Ultimately, knowing how prior stimuli affect current perception could help minimize perceptual errors or enhance smooth transition in haptic applications.

In conclusion, we showed serial dependence in haptic exploration for the first time where roughness and pleasantness of sandpapers shaped by the recent perceptual history. We found that serial dependence can be distinct for different perceptual attributes as we observed about 15% bias towards to recent stimuli for roughness and 5% away from the recent stimuli for pleasantness judgments. Furthermore, we observed that a more distant past also shapes haptic perception but in the opposite direction to the immediate past. We argue that serial dependence supports haptic perception and exploration by pooling sensory signals to reduce noise and guide perception. For this reason, we believe serial dependence provides a tool to render continuous experiences with dynamic stimulation or to gradually guide users towards a certain goal.

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